
ABANDONED PROJECTS IN RIVERS STATE: A MENACE TO DEVELOPMENT

By

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ABSTRACT

The scene of abandoned projects sparse across the expanse of Nigeria is alarming, ranging from roads, rails, factories, electricity and housing at all levels of government. Reports have it that Nigeria has become a dumping ground of abandoned projects and these projects worth billions of Naira. It therefore becomes of great concern that Nigeria so blessed with great potentials in the construction industry can experience such extent of abandonment of project. Project abandonment does not aid infrastructural growth or economic development of the state in any way, neither does it forestall development rather it results in lower living standard, inability of attracting foreign investors, lack of employment opportunities, resource wastage, decrease in the tempo of economic activities and lots more. Factors that necessitate project abandonment include Political Reasons, Corruption, Inflation, Poor Feasibility Report, Unaccountability etc. while the effect project abandonment are reduction in living standard, unemployment, reduction in government revenue, economic participation and disappointment to the populace/user of the project if it was completed.

Keywords: Abandoned Projects, Rivers State, Development Issues, Infrastructure

INTRODUCTION

Longman Dictionary (2005) defines abandon as “to stop doing something because there are too many problems and it is impossible to continue. Planning is the foremost thing to be done if projects are not to be abandoned but completely executed. According to Ogunsemi (1991), the successful completion of a project depends on adequate planning which also includes financial planning. The scene of abandoned projects sparse across the expanse of Nigeria is alarming, ranging from roads, rails, factories, electricity and housing at all levels of government. Abandoned projects include railways, roads, schools and Nigeria is littered with lots of abandoned projects. Osemanan (1987) reported that Nigeria has become the “world’s junk-yard of abandoned projects and these projects worth billions of Naira. It therefore becomes of great concern that Nigeria so blessed with great potentials in the construction industry can experience such extent of abandonment of project.

According to the report by Kotangora (1993), there are about over 4000 units of abandoned or uncompleted projects that belongs to the Federal government of Nigeria. The essence of Development is to satisfy a purpose in the life of a people and abandoned project stand as a major obstacle to the development process. Therefore there is the need project planning with a time schedule of commencement and completion. When a project commences and for some reasons stops, without completion over a long period of time it is said to have been abandoned. The abandonment of projects poses both environmental and socio-economic consequences and challenges. Project abandonment constitutes both environmental and socio-economic consequences and challenges. Project abandonment does not aid infrastructural growth or economic development of the state in any way, neither does it forestall development rather it results in lower living standard, decline in employment opportunities, reduction in the tempo of economic activities, resource wastage, difficulties in attracting foreign investors etc.

Since independence in Nigeria, successive government has come up with different programs to tackle developmental projects that could better the life of her citizens. Surprisingly, most of such projects and programs both at Local, State and Federal levels are often partially or completely abandoned. Ukpanyang (2011) observed that the reasons most often given by successive governments in Nigeria for such abandonment are the differences in party programs or manifesto.

The specific objectives of the study were to: Assess the causes of project abandonment in Nigeria. Evaluate the extent to which project abandonment affects Nigerian Economy. Identify ways of controlling incessant cases of project abandonment in Nigeria. The research attempted to provide answers to the questions: What are the causes of project abandonment in Nigeria? To what extent does project abandonment affect Nigerian economy? What are the ways of controlling incessant cases of project abandonment in Nigeria?

LITRATURE REVIEW

A project is labeled “abandoned” when the expected time or period of completion elapses and certain physical features are seen becoming obsolete or wearing out, in that it will attract cost for replacement. There are two-time lags, the short-term projects which run between one to two years and long-term projects which run between three to five years, as applicable. If a project is not completed within the scheduled time even when extra time and additional resources are added, it is labeled or tagged abandoned. Dawodu (1987:10) sees abandoned projects as that in which all activities are totally suspended. Akindoyemi (2005:315) opinion

deferred a bit, as he postulates that a project is never considered abandoned, rather the project must have been suspended as a result of the proprietor lack of fund to continue in the main time.

DEVELOPMENT

The concept of development does not have a generally acceptable definition; however, there are certain indices that depict development. Development is essentially an economic concept that has definite/ optimistic connotation; it involves the use of certain technical and economic measures to utilize available resources to instigate economic growth and improve people's quality of life. It means a qualitative change that is always value positive. Development cannot be achievable, without an increase or addition to the existing conditions.

Residential housing as a project is among unparalleled in terms of abandonment in Nigeria as the demand for its use is always on the increase in the country (Ankeli, et al, 2016). Housing industry as a major priority of government in Nigeria has faced persistent problems of project abandonment. Instances abound in the country of new governments initiating new housing projects without first rounding up or taking into consideration the huge public fund that might have been expended on the existing project they met. The result of this usually is the alarming rate of housing project abandonment (Dumo, 2017).

The aftereffect of project abandonment to clients, contractor and the national economy are usually monumental.

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted mixed method approach and case study to examine the effects of abandonment of developmental projects on the physical environment in Rivers state. The study used both primary and secondary source of data collection Questionnaire, Interviews and observations formed the primary source of data while textbooks and journals constituted the secondary data. Questionnaires and interviews were designed with valid characteristics to elicit relevant data for the study. The format of the questionnaire is designed to cover respondents' characteristics so as to justify reliability of data.

CAUSES OF PROJECT ABANDONMENT IN RIVERS STATE

Adeleke (2005) declares that conflicting government policies, lack of accountability, high level of corruption, unskilled contractors, inadequate building materials, infrastructural deficit and wrong choice of facility location and so on has been highlighted as some of the major causes of abandonment of projects. Imaga, (2003) and Hanachor (2012) highlight the mainspring of project abandonment as follows:

(a) Political Reasons: Most projects are political projects that were not initially meant to be completed. They were initiated merely to score some political points. Because of the reason for selecting such projects, proper feasibility studies of the project are not carried out (Imaga, 2003). For reasons of tribal political patronage, sensitive projects are mostly awarded to unqualified contractors or to political zones where the project would never survive with the aim to compensate for political support given from those areas. This automatically breeds inefficiency of such projects and eventually its abandonment (Hanachor, 2012).

(b) Corruption: Globally, Nigeria ranks high among the most corrupt nations of the world. Lots of projects are abandoned either because the funds made available for it are embezzled or because those whose duty it is to provide funds for its completion are not interested in

doing so because they cannot get their “kick-back”.

Even when old projects are abandoned, new ones are started because of the chances of getting “kick-backs” from the new (Imaga, 2003). Majority of contractors in order to win contracts, intentionally lower their quotation, only to apply for variation later. Those who go on with the project will recourse to the use of inferior materials or even deviate from the original project plan (Hanachor, 2012).

(c) Inflation: The inflationary trend in Nigeria, as in many other developing countries defies economic prediction. This makes it extremely difficult for projects to be adequately estimated, Imaga, 2003.

(d) Poor Feasibility Report: The essence of a feasibility report is to know the viability or non-viability of a project, but in some cases feasibility reporters are influenced to give positive reports for even obvious non-viable projects. This affects real implementation of the projects (Imaga, 2003).

Most projects usually require counterpart funding but when one or more parties to the funding fails the resultant effect will be insufficient funds for the project. Therefore, the project will definitely be abandoned (Hanachor, 2012).

(e) Lack of Accountability: Lack of accountability makes projects managers and politicians feel that they can do whatever they like with the project. If there is the custom of accountability those who mismanage projects will be blacklisted in society, thereby improving on the efficiency of project execution (Imaga, 2003).

EFFECT OF PROJECT ABANDONMENT ON NIGERIAN ECONOMY (A CASE OF RIVERS STATE).

Rivers state when created in 1967 witnessed military administration with Navy Commander Alfred Diète-Spiff as the pioneer administrator. That administration is known to have created an immeasurable infrastructural development in the state. It is noticed that amidst this wonderful performance, there was a monumental abandonment at Rivers State Government Secretariat complex where a ten story-building proposed for the Rivers State House of Assembly was abandoned for years. The magnificent Ultra-Modern Port Harcourt Civic Center.

These sites remained abandoned until its completion. Former University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital Site at Hospital Road, Port Harcourt. Port Harcourt Township. Monorail Terminal at the Old Port Harcourt Township Stadium site, situated close and adjacent to the Police Children School, Port Harcourt. The model Primary and Secondary Schools built by the past Administration. Housing quarters for civil servants littered all over the state.

The effect of project abandonment has lots of negative impact on the life of those whom the project if completed would have been beneficiary and it would have brought development to the community, State or the entire country as the case maybe. The effect could be seen as dissatisfaction of the populace/proposed users, high rise in unemployment, lower standard of living, resources are wasted, declining economic participation and revenue accruing to government and inability of government and individuals to attract foreign loans and credit facilities.

Environmental effects culminate into major socio-economic issues such as the health of living things and economic losses as abandoned project sites are hideouts for many anti-social activities, examples are kidnapping, rape, armed robbery, initiation into cultism and even ritual killings. Others include breeding of dangerous reptiles and rodents that aids the spread of diseases, environmental pollution through indiscriminate dumping of refuse by unscrupulous residents of the area, threat to neighborhood safety and defacing of neighborhood aesthetics/devaluation of adjoining properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings from the analyzed result showed causes of project abandonment are: lack of proper planning, insufficient fund/financing, inflation, bankruptcy of contractors and disparity of project scope, political factor, death of client, incompetent project manager, wrong estimate, inadequate cost control, faulty design, and delay in payment.

While the effects of project abandonment are: Despondency/ Dispiritedness of the populace/proposed users, lowering of standard of living, drastic reduction in employment opportunities. Resource wastage, lower revenue accruing to government, difficulties in attracting foreign loans, decrease in tempo of economic activities. Results from the study showed that government has lots of abandoned projects in the state.

Various factors including lack of reliable feasibility study, insufficient budget, change of political administrations, nepotism etc. are responsible for developmental projects abandonment. Also, there are several environmental consequences arising from project abandonment, which also create socio-economic effects. These include but not limited to social vices and untidy environment. It also posits that majority of abandoned development projects are public (government) projects. The study proposes the putting in place of legal framework that would regulate timely execution of projects. The application of environmentally sustainable security of abandoned sites as a guide to execution of developmental projects with a view to avoiding negative externalities that may arise from abandonment of projects.

The Monorail project in Rivers state was abandoned. The project costing over \$400 million was abandoned over 9 years. The success of the Monorail project could have generated a lot of Revenue to the state and human capital development that would have put the state in a position where it could have competed with state like Lagos and even the Federal Capital Territory. This therefore lays emphasis on the need for continuity in government. Abandonment of development project results in environmental and socio-economic impacts.

Environmental impacts associated with abandonment include visual impacts, landscape modification, erosion, biodiversity loss and pollution, all of which may commence as environmental issues and eventually result in significant environmental problems. Every project has a commencement and finishing time frame with which contract values are calculated. Nevertheless, out of sheer nepotism and corruption, particularly in the public sector where majority of abandonment takes place, development projects abandonment commonly abounds in Nigeria. Imperatively, it is observed that abandonment in the public sector is as a result of political influence and misguidance which arose from insufficient budgeting, lack of effective feasibility studies, change of political administration, nepotism and corrupt contract procedures.

Environmental effects culminate into major socio-economic issues such as the health of living things and economic losses as abandoned project sites are hideouts for many anti-social activities such as kidnapping, rape, armed robbery, initiation into cultism and even ritual killings. Others include breeding of dangerous reptiles and rodents that aids the spread of diseases, environmental pollution through indiscriminate dumping of refuse by unscrupulous residents of the area, threat to neighborhood safety and defacing of neighborhood aesthetics/devaluation of adjoining properties. This of course is the rationale for this study as stated earlier and had been a major issue in Nigeria in general and the Rivers state in Particular. Public sector projects are prone to problems of abandonment than those of private sectors and have been instrumental to significant economic losses, incompatibility of infrastructural development.

The teeming population of the study area, poor living standard, encouragement of social ills such as robbery, kidnap, rape and ritual practices as facilitated by the hideouts created by abandoned sites. Environmental issues are on the increase in Nigeria as poor sanitary conditions created by abandoned sites facilitated the breeding of disease carrying rodents that are responsible for the spread of dangerous diseases such as Lassa fever. The study had therefore underscored both socio-economic and environmental impacts of abandonment of development projects in the Port Harcourt Metropolis, investigative establishing the major causes of project abandonment and highlighted the various forms of socio-economic and environmental impacts associated with project abandonment.

CONCLUSION

Abandonment of projects are created by inadequate planning, inflation, poor financing delayed payment and political factor, incompetent project manager, wrong estimate, faulty design insufficient cost control. Effects of abandonment of projects are despondency/despisedness of the populace/ users, increased unemployment, resource wastage, lower standard of living decrease in the tempo of economic activities and a sharp decline in revenue to government.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance development, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Ensure thorough and transparent feasibility studies are conducted before the commencement of any project and this should include a detailed financial plan and risk assessment to anticipate potential challenges and inflation impacts.
2. Implement strict accountability measures for all stakeholders involved in the project lifecycle and promote regular audits and public disclosure of project progress and financial expenditures to deter corruption and mismanagement.
3. Develop and enforce laws that mandate the completion of projects, regardless of changes in political administration to reduce the frequency of project abandonment due to political reasons and ensure continuity.
4. Establish a dedicated fund for project completion and ensure that projects are adequately funded before they begin and also explore public-private partnerships and alternative funding sources to mitigate the risk of insufficient financing.
5. Award contracts based on merit and capability rather than political patronage, regularly vet and monitor contractors to ensure they have the necessary skills and resources to complete the projects.
6. Incorporate flexible budgeting mechanisms to account for inflation and other economic variables and regularly update project budgets and timelines based on current economic conditions.

7. Involve local communities and stakeholders in the planning and monitoring of projects, to foster a sense of ownership and ensure that projects are aligned with the actual needs and priorities of the populace.
8. Invest in the training and development of project managers and other key personnel and ensuring that projects are managed by qualified and competent individuals can significantly reduce the risk of abandonment.
9. Implement security measures to protect abandoned project sites from becoming hotspots for criminal activities. This can include regular patrols, proper fencing, and community surveillance initiatives.
10. Ensure that all projects incorporate environmental sustainability practices from the outset. This includes proper waste management, erosion control, and measures to protect local biodiversity.
11. Establish a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to track the progress of projects and carry out regular assessments to help identify potential issues early and facilitate timely interventions to prevent abandonment

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